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Consortium

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1	Trinity College Dublin (TCD)	Ireland
2	University of Murcia (UM)	Spain
3	Technical University of Vienna (TUW)	Austria
4	Chalmers University of Technology (CUT)	Sweden
5	University of Oxford (UO)	United Kingdom

Figure 1: **Device scheme and experimental setup.** (a) Device architecture used for developing the experimental technique to measure $\langle J \rangle$ and systematically it during the device operation. (b) Experimental setup. Taken from our arXiv preprint [1].

1 Introduction

One of the main objectives of ASPECTS is to experimentally demonstrate the violation of the classical thermodynamic uncertainty relation (TUR) in an open quantum system, i.e. measure a signal-to-noise ratio below the classical TUR bound [2]. Violation of this inequality – which we refer to as quantum-thermodynamic precision advantage (QTPA) – has profound implications for quantum technologies, with several immediate applications. The TUR bounds the fluctuations of an observed signal (e.g. a heat current) by the amount of dissipation needed to generate that signal. The bound is expressed in term of the entropy production. In the context of this report, this uncertainty can be expressed as

$$\frac{\text{Var}(J)}{\langle J \rangle^2} \geq 2 \frac{k_B}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where J is the heat current, σ is the entropy production and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. $\text{Var}(J)$ denotes the statistical variance of the quantity within the parenthesis. The quantity J in a cavity quantum electrodynamics (CQED) device is the electromagnetic power of microwave radiation flowing through the device as heat. The expected magnitude of $\langle J \rangle$ is of the order of 1 aW (10^{-18} aW) and less, defining the main challenge of these measurements. This measurements become more formidable to accurately measure $\text{Var}(J)$, on an already small signal strength of the mean $\langle J \rangle$.

This Deliverable report presents our methodology and results until now on the Task 1.3— experimental violation of classical TURs in a CQED device. Specifically, after having developed significant experimental capability, we report our measurements of $\langle J \rangle$ and $\text{Var}(J)$. We measure $\langle J \rangle$ for extremely weak microwave radiation with a precision of 0.05 attoWatts. We have systematically utilized and validated this technique in a related quantum thermal machine, leading to a manuscript submitted to the journal Physical Review X. The manuscript is currently available in the arXiv preprint server [1].

We have just developed and tested the technique to measure $\text{Var}(J)$ in a model device. This technique is supplemented with theoretical support by the TBD team led by Prof. Mark Mitchison. The next step is to deploy these techniques in a quantum thermal device where we expect to observe the violation. We have already begun the experiments on the target device at

Figure 2: **Quantum thermal machine and measurement of heat currents.** (a) Energy-level scheme of the quantum thermal machine which consists of two superconducting qubits connected to two microwave waveguides acting as heat baths. Differential power spectral density (PSD) represents the spectral profile of the heat currents radiated by the quantum thermal machine when operated as a (b) heat engine or (c) refrigerator. The total power is obtained by integrating the differential PSD.

the time of submission this report. Identifying this target device was also supported by the TBD team. We expect to have reach in a month to the corresponding milestone MS2: Demonstration of QTPA in an open quantum system.

2 Experimental results

The CUT team has investigated a superconducting circuit consisting of two superconducting transmon qubits coupled to microwave waveguides in a symmetry-selective way [Fig. 1(a)]. By applying dephasing noise to any one (frequency-tunable) qubit, we have utilized the machine as a refrigerator, heat engine, and thermal accelerator. Our experimental setup, shown in Fig. 1(b), places our device in the mixing chamber of a dilution refrigerator at a stable temperature of 10 mK. The device is shielded from external interference with several layers of electromagnetic protections. The main experiments were performed using a microwave transceiver with a powerful control interface of its FPGA logic, in which we can implement real-time digital signal processing necessary for the sensitive power measurements of the heat flow in the form of microwave radiation. We interleave measurements with the heat baths active and inactive, which facilitates significant elimination of noise in the measurement chain.

Heat baths are implemented through artificially synthesized thermal fields in the waveguides. To synthesize the thermal baths to our device, we use arbitrary waveform generators (Keysight 3202A) to synthesize white noise with a 30 MHz bandwidth, centered at 200 MHz, up-converted with IQ mixers and local oscillators.

We have studied the heat flows by measuring power spectral density (PSD) of the emitted microwave radiation in the waveguides, at a level and precision of 0.05 attoWatts (10^{-18} W) (see Figure 2). The PSD is calculated in real-time of the voltage readout acquired over the time period of 10 microseconds and is averaged over about 10 - 50 million repetitions. Furthermore, this measurement is interleaved with PSD measurement in the absence of the applied heat baths as a reference to discard noise contributed by our measurement circuit. To measure $\langle J \rangle$, the PSD needs to be integrated over the frequency domain. However this method is very time-consuming and highly inefficient owing to the bottleneck in processing calculating PSD in real-time that is performed in a stream process, external from the FPGA processor. We overcame this bottleneck by performing the integration over the time domain measurements on FPGA and the use of Parseval's theorem:

$$\langle J \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |S_{\{s,a\}}(\omega)|^2 d\omega = \int_0^{\infty} |f_{\{s,a\}}(t)|^2 dt \quad (2)$$

This method gives close to maximal computational efficiency in measuring $\langle J \rangle$, allowing us to

Figure 3: **Measurement of heat currents and its fluctuations in a simple CQED device.** (a) Device scheme containing a transmon with three levels and a waveguide. (b) Measured heat current, $\langle J \rangle$ and (c) variance in heat current, $\text{Var}(J)$, for the transition $|1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle$ as a function of two-photon $|0\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle$ pump power.

take the same number of high averages in a shorter experimental run-time, which was otherwise prohibitively long for the full study. This speed-up is particularly important for the accurate measurements of $\text{Var}(J)$. We measure it by real-time computation in the FPGA of:

$$\text{Var}(J) = \langle J^2 \rangle - \langle J \rangle^2 \quad (3)$$

To develop and test the technique to measure $\text{Var}(J)$, we study a simpler device consisting of a transmon coupled to a single waveguide (Figure 2). We strongly drive the two-photon transition $|0\rangle \rightarrow |2\rangle$, via a virtual level. We then study the cascade decay process $|2\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle$. This scheme allows us to study a simpler system driven by a coherent tone of frequency $(\omega_{01} + \omega_{12})/2$, while studying the emission at a different frequency (ω_{01}) . We measure both $\langle J \rangle$ and $\text{Var}(J)$ of the radiation emitted from the transition $|1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle$ [Figure. 3(b) and Figure. 3(c), respectively]. In this context, these quantities do not represent heat flow because the emission is coherent as opposed to incoherent emission in response to heat baths. However, this experiment allows us to validate the measurement technique in a well-understood device. We observe, as per expectation, $\langle J \rangle$ increases with increasing pump power, as it increasingly elevates the population of $|2\rangle$. We also observe that $\text{Var}(J)$ also increases with increasing pump power.

3 Current status

Having developed the experimental techniques to measure $\langle J \rangle$ and $\text{Var}(J)$, we move forward to deploy them in a device shown in Fig. 1(a). With support from the TBD team, we have identified that the operating regime where we anticipate the TUR to be violated. We will use the framework developed by TBD team [3] towards the validation. We have already cooled the device and the experiments have been started before the submission of this report.

References

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